

Original Research Article

Impact of regular physical activity and sport on the school performances of student between 6 and 10 years old

^{*1}Kheira Amina Bekhechi and ²Belkacem Khat

Abstract

¹Institut de l'Education Physique et Sportive, Université des Sciences et de la Technologie d'Oran Mohamed Boudiaf, Algérie

²Institut de l'Education Physique et Sportive, Université des Sciences et de la Technologie d'Oran Mohamed Boudiaf, Algérie

*Corresponding Author's E-mail:
bekhechia@hotmail.fr
Tel.: 00213 673 881 589

This longitudinal study seeks to show if sport has an impact on the school results and also on cognitive functioning, and if this causal link is significantly important. An experimental group of 55 students that practice out-of-school sports, at a rate of 3 times a week and a reference group of 55 students that do not practice out of school sports, their age is between 6 and 10 years old, both male and female from an elementary schools of the town of Oran (Algeria), they were followed during 15 month (five quarters). The socio-demographic data were collected by a questionnaire intended for the students of the two groups, and the administrative school results at the end of each quarter. An intelligence test of the CPM (Raven's Coloured Progressive Matrices) was administered at the end of the fifth trimester to assess the main cognitive abilities in both groups. Students that practice out-of-school sports have general school averages and a significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) level of intelligence than students that do not. As noted by many similar studies, the practice of a physical-activity and sport regular seem to have a very positive impact on the academic performance and also on cognitive functioning.

Keywords: Academic performance, Cognitive functioning, Physical-activity and sport, School performance, Students

INTRODUCTION

The practice of physical exercise was classically associated with improvements of the metabolic functions such as cardiovascular, ventilator, hormonal (Donnelly and Lambourne, 2011; Haapala et al. (2017). Recent evidence shows how the effects of the physical-activity on the brain can create positive results as the improvement of the attention, the memory and the executive functions (De Greeff et al., 2018; Esteban-Cornejo et al., 2015; Tomporowski et al., 2011; Van der Niet et al., 2014). These last years, many studies brought back the relation between the physical exercise and the notes obtained at primary, secondary and academic education levels (Álvarez-Bueno et al., 2016; Maureira

and Diaz, 2017).

Physical-activity seems to have a positive effect on other determinants of academic success like the behavior in class, the self-esteem, the self-image, satisfaction towards the school, the feeling of member ship of the school and their social interactions. Research showed that regular physical-activity improves the school results and the productivity of the students, just as their capacity to be focused for long periods (De Greeff et al., 2018). The daily physical-activity improves the output of the students and supports their academic success, stimulates their memory, their direction of observation and develops their capacity to solve problems and to

make decisions; it also clearly controls the problems of behavior, by adopting a positive attitude and by having the direction of the creativity (Álvarez-Bueno et al., 2016; Álvarez-Bueno et al., 2017; Bangsbo et al., 2016).

It is suggested that the beneficial effects of the physical-activity on the school output are ascribable to the improvement of the cognitive functions, such as the attention, the concentration and the working memory (Bezold et al., 2014; Esteban-Cornejo et al., 2014; Rasberry et al., 2011; Resaland et al., 2016).

This study sought to show if the regular sports activity has a positive impact on the school results and if this causal link is significant.

METHODS

Population

On the whole, 110 students of the two sexes from 6 to 10 years old of 16 elementary schools, in class of second and third year with return to school 2015/2016 were selected. Students who were involved in this study after the written approval by their parents and the administration of the school were divided into two groups: the experimental group (55 students) which profits from 3 weekly sessions of physical-activity and sport out-of-school and the reference group (55 students) which does not practice any out of school physical-activity and sport.

Experimental protocol

A survey previously distributed to all teachers confirmed and validated the choice of the classes concerned: each class had to include experienced sports students, members of sports clubs and non-sports students.

A direct interview with each student was conducted in order to select the two groups, the same age, the same sex and the same socio-demographic level.

These two groups were followed from the first to the fifth trimester during two school years (2015-2016 and 2016-2017), by means of a survey submitted after each quarter: the document contains socio-demographic, school and sports data for each student which is as follows:

- The social level (working and non-separated parents, number of siblings, no health problems, average number of sleeping hours per night)
- School averages out of 10 (quarterly and both subjects: mathematics and Arabic language), non-doubling, no tutoring;
- School and extracurricular sports (nature and time);

In addition, a test on cognitive functioning (the CPM: Raven's Coloured Progressive Matrices) (Raven (1998)) was carried out by the two groups of students (sporting students and non-sporting students) after the last

trimester (fifth quarter) and treated by a clinical psychologist.

Statistical method

Statistical analyses were carried out on the SPSS software. Comparisons of means were made by statistical tests of the type Mann-Whitney U (2 samples) and ANOVA at one factor. The comparison between the two groups and the level of intelligence were measured by the Likert scale. For all the tests carried out the threshold of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS

Statistically and according to the Mann-Whitney U test, the difference is very significant ($p < 0.05$) for all school averages between the two groups (Figure 1).

There is a large difference in the overall school averages between sporting students and non-sporting students. The general quarterly, mathematics and Arabic language averages of the five quarters of the sports group are significantly higher than those of the non-sporting group (Figure 1).

In fact, sporting students have a general quarterly average of five quarters of 8.93 out of 10 against 5.99 out of 10 among non-sporting students. For the general averages of the five quarters of mathematics and the Arabic language, the sports group has a general average of 9.16 out of 10 against 4.77 in mathematics and 8.88 against 4.89 out of 10 in Arabic language.

Thus, the correlation between the overall average of the five quarters and the overall average of the five mathematics scores ($r = 0.72$) is very strong. There is also a strong correlation ($r = 0.81$) between the overall average of the five quarters and the overall average of the five scores of the Arabic language. That is, the relationship between the overall quarterly average of the five quarters and the overall average of the 5 scores of the Arabic language is stronger than the relationship between the overall quarterly average of the 5 quarters and the overall average of the five marks of mathematics.

For sporting students, the quarterly average is constant from the first to the fifth quarter. While among non-sporting students, the quarterly average is decreasing from the first to the fifth quarter particularly in the 4th and 5th quarter. (Figure 2)

In the sports group, the general school averages of mathematics and the Arabic language are constant in the five quarters. While in the non-sports group there is a sharp decrease in the average in mathematics (from 5.43 to 3.96) and also for the Arabic language (from 5.28 to 4.4) in the five quarters. (Figure 3)

Statistically and according to the Likert scale, the difference is very significant ($p < 0.05$) between the two

Figure 1. Comparison by the Mann-Whitney U Test of the general school averages of the 5 quarters (out of 10) of the two sports and non-sports groups * P < 0.05

Figure 2. The evolution of the quarterly general averages of the 5 quarters (scores out of 10) of the two sports and non-sports groups

Figure 3. The evolution of the general school averages of mathematics and the arabic language of 5 quarters (scores of 10) of the two sports and non-sports groups

Table 1. Comparison between the two groups and the level of intelligence by the Likert scale

Level of intelligence	Sports students		Non-sports students	
	Numbers	Percentage	Numbers	Percentage
Superior	9	16.4 %	0	0 %
Aboveaverage	30	54.5 %	0	0 %
Way	16	29.1 %	47	83.9 %
Belowaverage	0	0 %	7	12.5 %
Subnormal	0	0 %	1	1.8 %
Total	55	100 %	55	100 %

groups for the level of intelligence. The Contingency coefficient $C_c = 60\%$. Sports students have an average intelligence "Above average" and non-sports students have a mean intelligence average.

There was a big difference in the level of intelligence between sports students and non-sports students (Table 1). It can be seen that 16.40% of sports students have a "Superior" level of intelligence compared to 0% of non-sports students. In addition, the level of intelligence "Above average" is 54.50% among sports students against 0% among non-sports students. In the non-sporting group, the level of intelligence "Medium" dominates with 85.50% against 29.10% at the sports group. Finally, we note that 1.80% of non-sports students

have a level of intelligence "Subnormal" (equals a student) against 0% in the sports group. (Table 1).

DISCUSSION

Students who practice regular physical activity and sports, and although from different schools, have a general school average that is higher than that of non-practitioners. Thus, it appears that regular physical activity can improve concentration and academic performance, or even improve math, reading and writing scores (Donnelly et al. (2017; Haapala et al., 2017). The students who do physical activity perform better in school

than those who do not (Singh et al., 2012; Van Dusen et al., 2011). In our study, this positive effect seems to be lasting since it is observed during the five school years of the study (Schmidt et al., 2017). On the other hand, the high level of intelligence level of sports students located "Above average" (54.50%) confirms to some extent the influence of regular physical and sports practice as well on the achieving better academic results than cognitive functioning.

In April 2017, 24 researchers from 8 different countries and different disciplines made a consensus statement on the benefits of physical activity on fitness, health, cognitive operation, the commitment, the motivation, the psychological wellness and the social inclusion of the children and the young ages from 6 to 18 years (Bangsbo et al., 2016; Morales et al., 2011). A positive association between the programs of physical exercises and academic performance has been reported more or less regularly in the literature and meta-analyzes (Álvarez-Bueno et al., 2016; Howie and Pate, 2012; Lambourne et al., 2013; Norris et al., 2015; Watson et al., 2017).

One of the elements which contribute to this durable influence seems to be the volume and the intensity of the meetings of sports (Marques et al., 2017; Oliveira et al., 2017; Tompkins et al., 2012; Wittberg et al., 2012). The very positive and stable school results in the time of the sporting students represent an additional argument to encourage the sporting practice out-of-school in the children (Sævarsson et al., 2017). This observation is more marked in mathematics compared to the arab language (Álvarez-Bueno et al., 2017). Admittedly the beneficial of physical-activity and sporting impact on the health of the young people is undeniable, like his effect on the mental one and the social relations (Coe et al., 2013; Oliveira et al., 2017; Tomporowski et al., 2015), nevertheless we think that there is in our schools of the factors which are determining in this irrefutable fact. The over-populated classes, of the teachers little trained (and sometimes not formed by the whole) in didactic, a motivation to study very low students make that the latter do not concentrate very well in their training what lead them to school results very right means. To this must be added the sedentariness of the majority of school children in elementary schools that do not benefit from physical activities (or very little) either inside the school or out of school.

In this direction the current guidelines for the physical-activity recommend that the children must take part in moderate regular physical-activities with vigorous during 60 minutes or more each day (Rasberry et al., 2011). The results of a psychological test (WISC: Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children) on intelligence show that students who receive 5 hours of physical education per week scored higher than students who received the minimum of 40 minutes of physical education per week (Janssen et al., 2011). This represents an additional argument for encouraging out-of-school sports activities

for children. Not only the children do not reach the level of physical-activity recommended, but the schools also contribute to this culture of physical inactivity (Donnelly and Lambourne, 2011; Morales et al., 2011). During last years, many school systems eliminated the recreations and / or physical education from their program of studies because of the increasing pressure to increase the school results (Watson et al., 2017)).

The regular physical-activity could contribute to improve the intellectual abilities (Marques et al., 2017; Oliveira et al., 2017; Van der Niet et al., 2014). It also improves the cognitive functions, in particular the concentration and the memorizing which one knows the importance in the processes of training (Donnelly et al., 2016; Esteban-Cornejo et al., 2015; Janssen et al., 2014; Maureira and Diaz, 2017; St-Louis-Deschênes and Ellemberg, 2013; Van der Fels et al., 2015). However the positive influence of this factor on the school behavior in general and results in particular is established for a long time (St-Louis-Deschênes and Ellemberg, 2013; Schmidt et al., 2017). The children who are in physical good condition could succeed until twice better on academic tests than those who are not in good physical condition (Sævarsson et al., 2017)).

Recent research shows the need to increase the physical-activity at the children and the teenagers which can be critical for the inversion of the current trends of the disease and also for the improvement of academic success (Bass et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2013; Telford et al., 2012; Tompkins et al., 2012)).

CONCLUSION

The regular physical-activity and sport deserve to be largely encouraged for the children, taking into account its benefits not only on health, but also on academic performance and cognitive functioning. It would be interesting in future research to determine what is the most influential component of physical activity and sport on school results to help educators (parents, teachers ...) to improve early learning.

REFERENCES

- Álvarez-Bueno C, et al. (2017). Academic achievement and physical activity: a meta-analysis. *American academy of pediatrics*, 140(6). doi: 10.1542/peds.2017-1498.
- Álvarez-Bueno C, et al. (2016). Association of physical activity with cognition, metacognition and academic performance in children and adolescents: a protocol for systematic review and meta-analysis. *BMJ Open*, 6(6). Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/bmjop-en-2016-011065>
- Bangsbo J, et al. (2016). The copenhagen consensus conference 2016: children, youth, and physical activity in schools and during leisure time. *Br J Sports Med*, 0, pp. 1–2. doi:10.1136/bjsports-2016-096325
- Bass RW, et al. (2013). Physical fitness and academic performance in middle school students. *Acta pædiatrica*, 102, 832–837.

- Bezold CP, et al (2014). The effects of changes in physical fitness on academic performance among New York City youth. *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 55(6), 774-781. doi: 10.1016/j.jadohealth.2014.06.006
- Chen LJ, et al. (2013). Fitness change and subsequent academic performance in adolescents. *J. Sch. Health*, 83(9), 631-638. retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.12075>
- Coe DP, et al. (2013). Physical fitness, academic achievement, and socioeconomic status in school-aged youth. *J. Health*. 83(7), 500-508. doi: 10.1111 / josh.12058.
- De Greeff JW, et al. (2018). Effects of physical activity on executive functions, attention and academic performance in preadolescent children: a meta-analysis. *J. Sci. Med. Sport*, 21(5), 501-507. doi: 10.1016 / j.jsams.2017.09.595. Epub 2017 Oct 10.
- Donnelly JE, et al. (2016). Physical activity, fitness, cognitive function, and academic achievement in children: a systematic review. *Med Sci Sports Exerc*, 48(6), 1197–1222. doi: 10.1249/MSS.0000000000000901.
- Donnelly JE, et al. (2017). Physical activity and academic achievement across the curriculum: results from a 3-year cluster-randomized trial. *US National Library of Medicine National Institutes of Health*, 99, 140-145. doi: 10.1016/j.yjmed.2017.02.006. Epub 2017 Feb 11.
- Donnelly JE, Lambourne K (2011). Classroom-based physical activity, cognition, and academic achievement. *Preventive Medicine*, 52, S36–S42. doi: 10.1016/j.yjmed.2011.01.021. Epub 2011 Jan 31
- Esteban-Cornejo I, et al. (2014). Independent and combined influence of the components of physical fitness on academic performance in youth. *J. Pediatr*, 165(2), 306-312. doi: 10.1016/j.jpeds.2014.04.044. Epub 2014 Jun 19.
- Esteban-Cornejo I, et al. (2015). Physical activity and cognition in adolescents: a systematic review. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 18(5), 534-539. retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2014.07.007>
- Haapala EA, et al. (2017). Physical activity and sedentary time in relation to academic achievement in children. *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport*, 20(6), 583–589. doi: 10.1016/j.jsams.2016.11.003
- Howie EK, Pate RR (2012). Physical activity and academic achievement in children: a historical perspective. *J. Sport and Health Sci.*, 1(3), 160-169. doi: 10.1016 / j.jshs.2012.09.003
- Janssen M, et al. (2014). A short physical activity break from cognitive tasks increases selective attention in primary school children aged 10-11. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 7(3), 129-134. doi: 10.1016/j.mhpa.2014.07.001
- Lambourne K, et al. (2013). Indirect and direct relations between aerobic fitness, physical activity, and academic achievement in elementary school students. *Mental Health and Physical Activity*, 6(3), 165-171. doi: 10.1016/j.mhpa.2013.06.002
- Marques A, et al. (2017). Association between physical education, school-based physical activity, and academic performance: a systematic review. *Retos*, 31, 316-320.
- Maureira F, Diaz HM (2017). Physical Exercise and Academic Performance. *MOJ Sports Med*, 1(4), 90–92. doi: 10.15406/mojism.2017.01.00021
- Morales J, et al. (2011). Relation between physical activity and academic performance in 3rd-year secondary education students. *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 113(2), 539-546. doi: 10.2466/06.11.13.PMS.113.5.539-546.
- Norris E, et al. (2015). Physically active lessons as physical activity and educational interventions: a systematic review of methods and results. *Prev. Med*, 72, 116–125. doi: 10.1016/j.yjmed.2014.12.027.
- Oliveira T, et al. (2017). Cardiorespiratory fitness, but not physical activity, is associated with academic achievement in children and adolescents. *Annals of Human Biology*, 44(4), 309-315. retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/03014460.2017.1308010>
- Rasberry CN, et al. (2011). The association between school-based physical activity, including physical education, and academic performance: a systematic review of the literature. *Preventive Medicine*, 52, S10–S20. doi: 10.1016/j.yjmed.2011.01.027
- Raven JC (1998). *Raven's Coloured Progressive Matrices (CPM). Section 1 General Overview*. 1998 Edition, Updated 2003.
- Resaland GK, et al. (2016). Effects of physical activity on schoolchildren's academic performance: The Active Smarter Kids (ASK) cluster-randomized controlled trial. *Preventive Medicine*, 91, 322–328. doi: 10.1016/j.yjmed.2016.09.005
- Sævarsson ES, et al. (2017). Organized leisure-time sport participation and academic achievement in preadolescents. *Scand J Public Health*. 45 (8), 861-868. doi: 10.1177 / 1403494817705560. Epub 2017 Jun 30.
- Schmidt M, et al. (2017). Disentangling the relationship between children's motor ability, executive function and academic achievement. retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0182845>
- Singh A, et al. (2012). Physical activity and performance at school: a systematic review of the literature including a methodological quality assessment. *Arch. Pediatr. Adolesc. Med.* 166 (1), 49–55. doi: 10.1001/archpediatrics.2011.716.
- St-Louis-Deschênes M and Ellemberg D (2013). L'exercice physique aigu et la performance cognitive chez l'enfant et l'adolescent. *Science & Sports*, 28, 57-64. doi: 10.1016/j.scispo.2011.10.007
- Telford RD, et al. (2012). Physical education, obesity, and academic achievement: a 2-year longitudinal investigation of Australian elementary school children. *Ame. J. Pub. Health*, 102(2), 368–374. doi: 10.2105/AJPH.2011.300220
- Tompkins CL, et al. (2012). The effect of an unstructured, moderate to vigorous, before-school physical activity program in elementary school children on academics, behavior, and health. *BMC Public Health*, 12, 300. doi: 10.1186 / 1471-2458-12-300.
- Tomporowski PD, et al. (2015). Exercise and children's cognition: The role of exercise characteristics and a place for metacognition. *Journal of Sport and Health Science*, 4(1), 47-55. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jshs.2014.09.003>
- Tomporowski PD, et al. (2011). Physical activity interventions and children's mental function: an introduction and overview. *Preventive Medicine*, 52, S3–S9. doi: 10.1016 / j.yjmed.2011.01.028. Epub 2011 21 mars.
- Van der Fels I, et al. (2015). The relationship between motor skills and cognitive skills in 4–16 year old typically developing children: A systematic review. *J. Sci. Med. Sport*, 18(6), 697–703. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2014.09.007>
- Van der Niet AG, et al. (2014). Modeling relationships between physical fitness, executive functioning, and academic achievement in primary school children. *Psychology of Sport and Exercise*, 15(4), 319-325. doi: 10.1016/j.psychsport.2014.02.010
- Van Dusen DP, et al. (2011). Associations of physical fitness and academic performance among schoolchildren. *J. Sch. Health*, 81(12), 733-740. doi: 10.1111 / j.1746-1561.2011.00652.x.
- Watson A, et al. (2017). Effect of classroom-based physical activity interventions on academic and physical activity outcomes: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int. J. Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 14(1), 114. doi: 10.1186/s12966-017-0569-9.
- Wittberg RA, et al. (2012). Children's aerobic fitness and academic achievement: a longitudinal examination of students during their fifth and seventh grade years. *Ame. J. Pub. Health*, 102(12), 2303-2308.